

PRISMA-ScR Checklist — Completed

*Seven Versus Fourteen Days for Resistant Bloodstream Infections: What Do We Actually Know?
A Scoping Review*

Reporting standard: Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, et al. PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation. *Ann Intern Med.* 2018;169(7):467–473. doi:10.7326/M18-0850

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This checklist documents compliance with each of the 22 items of the PRISMA-ScR reporting guideline. Page numbers refer to the *Revised Manuscript* submitted alongside this checklist.

#	Item	PRISMA-ScR checklist requirement	Compliance — where reported in the manuscript and this protocol
TITLE			
1	Title	Identify the report as a scoping review.	Title reads: “ <i>Seven Versus Fourteen Days for Resistant Bloodstream Infections: What Do We Actually Know? A Scoping Review.</i> ” The phrase “A Scoping Review” is explicitly included in the title.
ABSTRACT			
2	Structured summary	Provide a structured summary that includes (as applicable): background, objectives, eligibility criteria, sources of evidence, charting methods, results, and conclusions.	Abstract (Purpose, Methods, Results, Conclusion). Purpose shortened to 58 words in the revised version; Results now integrates randomized, meta-analytic and observational findings and reports the full 28-study decomposition (6 RCT + 6 meta-analyses + 15 observational + 1 post-hoc) aligned with Figure 1.
INTRODUCTION			
3	Rationale	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known. Explain why the review questions/objectives lend themselves to a scoping review approach.	Introduction (paragraphs 1–4). Explicit justification for a scoping review over a systematic review is given in the last Introduction paragraph and in Methods (“Study Design and Framework”) citing Munn et al. (2018).
4	Objectives	Provide an explicit statement of the questions and objectives being addressed with reference to their key elements (e.g.,	End of Introduction states the primary objective; Methods (“Study Design and Framework”) states the PCC-framed research question verbatim. Full PCC breakdown reported in §3 of the

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		population or participants, concepts, and context) or other relevant key elements used to conceptualize the review questions and/or objectives.	deposited protocol.
METHODS			
5	Protocol and registration	Indicate whether a review protocol exists; state if and where it can be accessed (e.g., a Web address); and if available, provide registration information, including the registration number.	Methods (“Study Design and Framework”) and Limitations. The protocol was not registered a priori in a public registry because PROSPERO does not accept scoping review protocols. The pre-specified internal protocol (finalized 15 January 2026, 31 days before the search) has been deposited in Zenodo (CERN repository) with DOI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19641610 and is publicly accessible; also available from the corresponding author upon request.
6	Eligibility criteria	Specify characteristics of the sources of evidence used as eligibility criteria (e.g., years considered, language, and publication status), and provide a rationale.	Methods (“Eligibility Criteria”). Full criteria also in §5 of the deposited protocol: RCT / meta-analyses / observational studies with confounding adjustment; adults ≥ 18 y; BSI with minimum 3-day difference between shorter and longer arms; English only; no lower date limit.
7	Information sources	Describe all information sources in the search (e.g., databases with dates of coverage and contact with authors to identify additional sources), as well as the date the most recent search was executed.	Methods (“Literature Search”). PubMed searched on 15 February 2026; supplemented by hand-search of reference lists of included studies, meta-analyses and relevant guidelines. Single-database searching acknowledged as a limitation.
8	Search	Present the full electronic search strategy for at least 1 database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	Methods (“Literature Search”) reproduces the full PubMed search string verbatim (also in §6.2 of the deposited protocol). No limits or filters applied.
9	Selection of sources of evidence	State the process for selecting sources of evidence (i.e., screening and eligibility) included in the scoping review.	Methods (“Eligibility Criteria”): two independent reviewers screened titles, abstracts, and full texts; disagreements resolved by discussion with a third reviewer. Full procedure in §8 of the

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10	Data charting process	Describe the methods of charting data from the included sources of evidence (e.g., calibrated forms or forms tested by the team before use, and whether data charting was done independently or in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	Methods (“Data Charting”). Items extracted: design, sample size, setting, pathogen distribution, resistance data, duration definitions, outcomes, statistical methods. The data-charting form (spreadsheet of all 38 references) has been deposited in Zenodo (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.19641610).
11	Data items	List and define all variables for which data were sought and any assumptions and simplifications made.	Methods (“Data Charting”) lists variables. Terminology for β -lactamase-mediated resistance (ESBL vs ESBL/AmpC) is addressed in a dedicated clarifying sentence at the opening of the ESBL paragraph of the Evidence Map and in the footnote of Table 1.
12	Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence	If done, provide a rationale for conducting a critical appraisal of included sources of evidence; describe the methods used and how this information was used in any data synthesis (if appropriate).	Methods (“Data Charting”) states that no formal risk-of-bias or quality appraisal was performed, consistent with scoping review methodology (Arksey & O’Malley; Levac et al.; Munn et al.). This is also listed in Limitations.
13	Synthesis of results	Describe the methods of handling and summarizing the data that were charted.	Results (“Overview”); dedicated subsections “Randomized Controlled Trials” and “Meta-analyses” (new in the revised version); “Observational Evidence: Resistance-Related Findings”; and “Evidence Map by Resistance Category”. The Evidence Map presents randomized evidence before observational evidence within each of the five resistance categories, with study design stated for every citation.
RESULTS			
14	Selection of sources of evidence	Give numbers of sources of evidence screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at	Figure 1 (PRISMA-ScR flow diagram). 1,172 PubMed records + 3 hand-search records, 1 duplicate removed, 1,174 screened, 1,116 excluded at title/abstract, 58 full-text assessed, 30

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		each stage, ideally using a flow diagram.	excluded with reasons (9 no duration comparison, 8 duplicate/overlapping cohort, 5 no BSI-specific outcomes, 5 protocol/survey, 2 review/editorial, 1 narrative review), 28 studies included. Reported in Results (“Overview”) in full alignment with Figure 1.
15	Characteristics of sources of evidence	For each source of evidence, present characteristics for which data were charted and provide the citations.	Table 1 (RCTs; new “Ref” column added in revision linking each row to its citation). Table 2 (observational studies). Table 3 (meta-analyses).
16	Critical appraisal within sources of evidence	If done, present data on critical appraisal of included sources of evidence (see item 12).	Not applicable — no critical appraisal performed (see item 12).
17	Results of individual sources of evidence	For each included source of evidence, present the relevant data that were charted that relate to the review questions and objectives.	Tables 1–3 provide row-level results. Narrative synthesis in Results (new subsections “Randomized Controlled Trials” and “Meta-analyses”) and in the Evidence Map.
18	Synthesis of results	Summarize and/or present the charting results as they relate to the review questions and objectives.	Results section: “Evidence Map by Resistance Category” (5 categories: ESBL-E, CPE, MRSA, VRE, MDR non-fermenters), each structured as “Randomized evidence” → “Observational evidence” with study design stated for every citation. Overall synthesis in Table 4 (evidence map).
DISCUSSION			
19	Summary of evidence	Summarize the main results (including an overview of concepts, themes, and types of evidence available), link to the review questions and objectives, and consider the relevance to key groups.	Discussion (paragraphs 1–6): identifies the disconnect between where evidence is strongest (susceptible BSI) and where it is most needed (resistant BSI), discusses the per-protocol signal of OPTIMISE, and addresses the clinical question facing physicians treating ESBL-E, KPC-producing <i>K. pneumoniae</i> , and other resistant BSI.
20	Limitations	Discuss the limitations of the scoping review process.	Limitations section covers: single-database search, three meta-analyses identified only through hand-search, absence of a priori public registration (with mitigation via Zenodo deposit (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.19641610)),

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			absence of risk-of-bias appraisal, unreported resistance prevalence in definitive RCTs, English-only publications.
21	Conclusions	Provide a general interpretation of the results with respect to the review questions and objectives, as well as potential implications and/or next steps.	Conclusions section: reaffirms noninferiority for susceptible BSI; highlights the absence of powered evidence for resistant BSI; and explicitly warns against equating absence of evidence with evidence of equivalence. “Future Research” subsection identifies BALANCE+ and SHORTEN-2 as the priority paths forward.
FUNDING			
22	Funding	Describe sources of funding for the included sources of evidence, as well as sources of funding for the scoping review. Describe the role of the funders of the scoping review.	Declarations (Funding): financed by European Union – Next Generation EU and MUR through PRIN 2022 project PRIDE (codice 2022LP77J4_003; CUP F53D23000630006). Funders had no role in study design, data extraction, analysis, or reporting. Funding of the included primary studies is reported in the respective source publications.

Checklist compiled by V. Zuccaro, E. Asperges, and P. Valsecchi on behalf of all authors. Deposited in Zenodo (CERN repository) with permanent DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19641610> as supplementary material to the revised manuscript.